

Fragmented Relationships: A Study of Family Disintegration in Mohan Rakesh's *Adhe Adhure (Half Way House)*

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Abstract:

Mohan Rakesh's *Adhe Adhure* (1969) is one of the most powerful plays in modern Hindi drama that portrays vividly emotional and moral disintegration of urban middle class family in modern India. The research paper presents the breakdown of familial bonds and collapse of familial values in modern urban India. The play powerfully portrays the incomplete individual and the incomplete family. The household is represented by Savitri, Mahendranath and their children. The play is an example of the deconstruction of the conventional concept of family due to economic pressures, psychological conflicts and moral crisis.

Keywords: Family, Deconstruction, Fragmentation, Disintegration, Moral Crisis, Values.

Introduction:

The twentieth century is remarkable as there is a great transformation in the life of people all over the globe due to globalization, industrialization and fast-growing materialism. This has definitely affected the institution of marriage and family. The later half of the 20th century has depicted this change quite minutely in literature. This has definitely reflected in Indian life and literature. The 20th century modern drama is not an exception to this. Due to economic, socio-cultural, psychological changes the institution of family drastically changed. Mohan Rakesh, a leading Indian dramatist portrays this change minutely in *Adhe Adhure*.

Mohan Rakesh, a key figure of the *Navi Kahani* movement, is a remarkable playwright, a short story writer and a novelist in Hindi literature. He has excellent narrative power which exhibits in his novels and short stories. Still, he is more famous for his plays *Ashadh ka Ex din* (1958) *Leharonke Rajhans* (1963) and *Adhe Adhure* (1969). His drama displays contemporary

urban angst. Mohan Rakesh's plays are quite realistic and dealt with the problems and pressures of urban middle class people who are sandwiched in tradition and modernity. His art of characterization is unique. *Adhe Adhure* is the most celebrated play, renowned for its departure from harmonious *ghar* (home) of cultural imagination.

Adhe-Adhure was written in 1968 and first staged on 2nd march, 1969. The play is translated into English under the title *Half Way House* by Bindu Batra. Along with English, the play is translated and performed in all major languages of India. The play illustrates the utter rottenness of value system and total helplessness and despair of Indian middle-class family. Here, family becomes a site of intense conflict, emotional bankruptcy and existential despair and ultimately disintegration.

Family is supposed to be a fundamental unit of society representing love, trust, sacrifice and moral values. But in the modern life the same family becomes a site of conflict, self-

centredness, fragmentation and disintegration. Here, relationships are not marked by love, empathy and sacrifice but hostility, distrust and emotional distance. Due to urbanization, globalization, materialism and shifting gender roles family relationships are in danger. The family in *Adhe Adhure* is hollow and deconstructed because of all these reasons.

In India, traditionally family was viewed as a sacred institution based on mutual support, respect and emotional unity. In the joint family there was collective responsibility. The patriarchy represented father as the bread winner and head of the family and mother, a nurturing figure. In the modern periods in nuclear families, we see the shift in responsibilities. Women shared economic responsibilities too. Instead of 'we feeling,' individuality was supposed to be more important. The harmonious family transformed into disturbed-disintegrated one. This collapse of family structure is very well depicted by Mohan Rakesh in *Adhe Adhure*.

The play focuses on the dysfunctional family of Savitri and Mahendranath. Savitri is trapped in the bitter marriage with Mahendranath who is a failed businessman, unable to support the family economically due to a heavy loss in business, hence Savitri, the only bread winner is overburdened as she has to make a balance of her responsibilities towards her home as well as fulfil the economy. Ashok, her son is lazy, unemployed and always disillusioned. He has lost his desire to progress. Both the daughters, Binni with her unsuccessful marriage and Kinni the rebellious teenager are frustrated. Binni has married the boy of her choice but the marriage proves to be unsuccessful and she comes back where as Kinni is always unsatisfied and feels insecure in the suffocated atmosphere of the house. Savitri's attempts to change Mahendranath and other members in the family has proved unsuccessful. She is the only person who

struggles hard to keep the family from drowning in penury. She is fed up of Mahendranath, hence searches for fulfilment in other men like Singhanian (her boss), Jagmohan (her friend) and Juneja (former partner of Mahendranath). Unfortunately, she cannot find solace and understands that the mindsets of all the men are same. She embodies the modern Indian woman strained to breaking point by conflicting demands, societal expectations, economic responsibility, emotional starvation and personal despair. Her quest for a "complete man" is ultimately a quest for complete life which the institution of marriage has failed to provide. Savitri becomes a symbol of all the modern working women who are dominant.

All the members in the family are callous, lethargic and parasites. Their relationship is bitter, no understanding and no bonding. The play depicts emotional insecurities of children from a disintegrating family. The home for five members becomes a temporary unsatisfactory shelter for emotionally displaced individuals. There is no transmission of values, affection and wisdom among family members. Everybody is selfish and self-centred. Any family lives happily when the members think of others, give hand to other members of family but here we see that all the members sneer, taunt and insult each other. Not a single member is aware of Savitri's struggle. The home that the spectators watch is disordered, messy and disorganised. The play highlights the collapse of family as a unit of cultural and moral transmission. The 'home' has become absurd and fragmented 'house.' Savitri proves unsuccessful in bringing order in her own life and in the lives of her children.

One of the most significant aspects of the play is the emotional alienation among family members. Every character represents isolated island. The warmth and security in the home disappears and bitter loneliness remains.

Mahendranath feels insulted and gets no respect from his wife and children. He doesn't get respect and support and that is why he has lost all his wish to start a new. The young generation feels hopelessness. The constant conflict between the husband and wife, selfishness of children, insecurity, economic dependence and emotional instability make the family troubled. All the characters are incomplete individuals and blame others. Savitri is in search of a complete man forgetting the flaws within her. The family itself becomes a "halfway house" – a temporary space where individuals live together without genuine connection. The title suggests and reinforces the existential emptiness and incompleteness of modern urban life.

Through this play Mohan Rakesh harshly criticizes modern life especially middle-class life. The change in values bring money centred materialistic attitude which ultimately results in pessimistic hollowness. Family gets stability in living and sacrificing for others. Caring and sharing, respect and support, love and empathy and help and co-operation are foundations of a good family, at the same time the woman holds the family together. But when gender roles become dominant, ambitions kill love and empathy, self-centredness and selfishness take place of sacrifice, the family and familial values begun to collapse, the moral and emotional fabric of family weakens and traditional values disappear, the breakdown of family is sure!

At the end of the play Mahendranath, broken and frustrated returns to home. Despite the intense, toxic and abusive nature of their marriage, Savitri and Mahendranath are forced to accept that they cannot live with each other but

also cannot live without each other. The play leaves the audience with a sense of hopelessness, highlighting that the search for perfection in relationships is futile and the characters are destined to remain incomplete.

Rakesh offers no redemption or reconciliation. The family is still trapped in their "hell." The final image of Mahendranath and Savitri mechanically performing their empty routine with their children is one of the profound desolations. The values have disintegrated, leaving behind only the hollow shell of the family structure. Cohabitation means not family. The writer effectively captures the erosion of traditional values without romanticizing modern alternatives. This change leads psychological turmoil of modern urban life, making the play a timeless study of human incompleteness and familial disintegration.

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